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Research on Digital Marketing for Play Nutrition's Nutrition Bar

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Abstract

In the 4.0 context, Digital Marketing becomes suitable for all businesses, from small to medium to large, helping businesses reduce costs, increase the effectiveness of communication tools, and align with today's digital transformation context. The study examines the degree of application of Digital Marketing tools for the Play Nutrition bar. The results show that "Content Marketing" has the highest frequency of appearance, attractiveness, and influence. Along with "Content Marketing", "Video Marketing" also has the strongest impact. Based on the theoretical study of Digital Marketing, combined with survey results and orientation toward the use of Digital Marketing tools in the future for Play Nutrition bars, the research team proposes some recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of using Digital Marketing tools for Play Nutrition bars.

Keywords: Marketing, Digital Marketing, Nutrition bar, Play Nutrition

1. Raising the Issue

Marketing is a socially oriented management process, through which individuals and groups obtain what they need and desire through creating, offering, and exchanging valuable products with others (Philip Kotler & Armstrong, 2007).

E-Marketing is the process of planning for products, pricing, distribution, and promotion of products, services, and ideas to meet the needs of organizations and individuals based on electronic media and the internet (Philip Kotler, 2007). The application of the internet and related digital technologies combined with traditional media to achieve marketing objectives (Chaffey, 2012).

In the 4.0 era, consumer behavior has changed: from going to traditional stores, to online ordering from e-commerce websites and purchasing from online trading platforms. Digital Marketing is suitable for all businesses, from small to medium to large, helping them reduce costs, enhance the effectiveness of communication tools, and adapt to the current digital transformation context.

In this study, the research team examines the extent of the application of Digital Marketing tools at Play Nutrition to consider:

- The frequency of appearance of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools.
- The level of appeal of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools.
- The influence level of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools.

To examine these issues, the team surveyed 415 consumers in major cities in Vietnam using a random, convenient method.

The survey was constructed using a 5-point Likert scale, with:

1. *Never/ Very unappealing/ Very uninfluential*
2. *Rarely/ Unappealing/ Not influential*
3. *Sometimes/ Normal/ Moderate*
4. *Often/ Appealing/ Influential*
5. *Very often / Very appealing / Very influential*

After constructing the survey, the research team proceeded to interview the leaders of Play Nutrition. The survey was refined based on the feedback from the interviewees, and subsequently, the research team conducted a random pilot survey with 10 customers. Based on in-depth interviews and the preliminary survey, the research team finalized the survey and carried out a broader survey through this link (<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe7EZeZxmzVIw2XPMR7NNjGN5uy8W4al2-L3OifY9Y1Knrl7w/viewform>) with consumers in major cities of Vietnam. From the survey results, the research team proposes some measures to enhance the effectiveness of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools.

2. Theoretical Basis on Digital Marketing

2.1. Some definitions

2.1.1. Marketing

Marketing is a socially oriented management process, through which individuals and groups obtain what they need and desire by creating, offering, and exchanging valuable products with others (Philip Kotler & Armstrong, 2007). Marketing is the process of planning and executing the creation, pricing, promotion, and distribution of ideas, goods, and services to facilitate transactions that meet the objectives of individuals and organizations (AMA, The American Marketing Association, 2017). Marketing is the economic and social mechanisms that organizations and individuals use to satisfy their needs and desires through the exchange process of products in the market (Nguyen Thi Thu Thuy, 2008).

2.1.2. Digital Marketing

E-Marketing is the process of planning for products, pricing, distribution, and promotion of products, services, and ideas to meet the needs of organizations and individuals based on electronic media and the Internet (Philip Kotler, 2007). Internet marketing and online advertising, also known as e-marketing, web marketing, online marketing, or e-marketing, is advertising products and services via the Internet (Ruzic, D. 2003). The application of the Internet and related digital technologies combined with traditional media to achieve marketing objectives (Chaffey, 2012).

Internet marketing and the use of the internet and other digital technologies, combined with traditional methods, to achieve marketing objectives (Chaffey, D., Ellis-Chadwick, F., Mayer, R., Johnston, K., 2009). Online marketing is the practice of using information technology tools instead of traditional communication tools to conduct the marketing process (Le Si Tri, 2018). Digital Marketing: encompasses all activities to satisfy the needs and desires of customers through the internet and electronic media (Joel Reedy, Shauna Schullo, Kenneth Zimmerman 2000).

Electronic marketing involves the use of the internet and electronic devices such as personal computers, handheld computers, etc. to conduct marketing activities aimed at achieving the organization's objectives and maintaining customer relationships by enhancing understanding about them (information, behavior, values, loyalty levels, etc.). From there, promotional activities are carried out targeting specific objectives and online services to satisfy customer needs (PR Smith & Dave Chaffey, 2005). Electronic marketing is the use of information technology for marketing activities and is also the process of creating, communicating, transmitting, and changing values for customers, consumers, partners, and society as a whole (Strauss & Frost, 2008).

2.2. The Necessity of Digital Marketing

Digital Marketing helps promote products, interact with customers, and increase sales revenue. The necessity of Digital Marketing: The goal of Digital Marketing is to increase brand recognition, build trust, and boost sales conversions based on digital means. This goal will be implemented based on a specific Strategic Plan and suitable Digital Marketing Channels. (OCD, 2023)

2.2.1. Optimizing cost-effectiveness, saving budget

Businesses do not have to incur costs for traditional storefronts, rent spaces, kiosks, or traditional advertising costs like leaflets, signs, magazines. In the context of the 4.0 era, consumer behavior has changed. Instead of visiting traditional stores, they now order online from e-commerce websites and buy products on e-commerce platforms. Traditional marketing methods will cause businesses to incur high costs, usually carried out by big companies with strong financial capacities. Digital Marketing is suitable for all businesses, from small to medium to large (Adsmo, 2022).

2.2.2. Expanding the market, easily targeting potential customers

Digital Marketing makes it easier for businesses to market to customers without barriers, allowing marketing anywhere, anytime, and to any audience, simplifying the buying process for customers. Customers can learn about prices, view product images, and make payments without having to visit the store in person. It can be said that digital marketing has blurred geographical distances and territorial boundaries, expanding the market globally (Adsmo, 2022).

2.2.3. Measuring the information, determining the effectiveness more accurately

Digital Marketing will provide statistics and measure specific data using tools to guide marketers, allowing them to adjust their marketing strategy most appropriately. It helps in understanding and evaluating consumer behavior, identifying needs, gender, habits, the mode of access, the duration of access, and the content that users read on the website (Adsmo, 2022).

2.2.4. Promoting the brand recognition

It can be easily seen that digital marketing is a powerful tool for businesses to increase brand recognition among customers and users. Digital marketing has gradually touched the lives of customers, enhancing awareness about the business's brand, and creating a solid impression in the minds of the customers. Promotional and communication activities on television, phones, and the Internet contribute to broadening the business's brand presence, providing free PR, creating a bandwagon effect, and fostering goodwill for the brand (adsmo, 2022).

2.2.5. Competitiveness

In today's competitive business market, digital marketing has become an indispensable factor for businesses. Digital marketing tools and strategies help businesses enhance their competitive ability and create a distinction in the market. Thanks to digital marketing, businesses can elevate their market vision and knowledge, aiding in

making intelligent and effective business decisions. This enhances the business's competitive ability in the market while simultaneously setting them apart from its competitors (ooc.vn, 2022).

2.3. Digital marketing tools

According to Asialion (2020) and BetterGrowth (2023), there are several Digital marketing tools such as:

Social Media Marketing (Marketing through social media) Social media marketing is the use of social media platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, Zalo, TikTok, etc., to promote products or services.

Influencer/ Affiliate is a form of promoting products or services that a provider wants to convey through online promotional channels of money-making partners (publishers) to customers.

Multimedia Marketing (multimedia marketing): is the production of content to be posted on various media channels, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of marketing.

Search Engine Optimization (SEO): is the process of implementing methods to improve the ranking of a website in the results pages of search engines (the most popular being Google).

Video Marketing: Using video to market a product or service.

Content marketing: This is a marketing method with a strategy focused on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain customers.

Blog marketing is a form of marketing and advertising for brands, websites, products, etc., through blogging platforms.

3. An Overview of Play Nutrition and Play Nutrition Bars

3.1. An Overview of Play Nutrition

Play's mission: *Play is not just a brand; but a lifestyle, a dynamic and modern lifestyle, always filled with energy to conquer challenges yet always maintaining a healthy heart, a peaceful mind, and a happy life. **PLAY** spreads this lifestyle to every employee, every business partner, every distributor agent, and every customer.*

To achieve this, Play continuously strives to introduce wholesome nutrition products and uses these products as a bridge from the company to the customers because "You are what you eat"!

Figure 1. Logo và Tagline Play Nutrition

Source: Play Book (2023)

2015: Play began distributing the SSP energy bar imported from the UK. Upon its introduction, the product entered a niche market and was distributed to golf courses nationwide.

2016: Contracted the manufacturing of the Protein bar from Bulgaria. Continued to distribute Play Protein Bar to over 200 gyms nationwide.

2019: Began producing their first energy bar, the Play Energy Bar. Play sponsored major marathon events such as the Vnexpress Marathon, VPBank Marathon, Techcombank Marathon, and LongBien Marathon.

2020-2021: Play became a well-known name amongst most athletes. Play supported the country in the fight against the pandemic!!!

2022: Launched a Natural and healthy product for the mass market. Started distribution through MT channels: Winmart, Win+, BigC, CircleK, Family Mart, etc.

2023: Introduced a strategic product. Expanded distribution on the GT channel.

ACHIEVEMENTS

Introduced the term “Energy Bar” and initiated the movement to produce and market this product in Vietnam. Persuading golf course and gym operators, along with their clientele, that nutrition bars are integral to their activities is essential for transforming the dietary habits of golfers, gym enthusiasts, and runners in Vietnam. Showing the biggest players in the retail market in Vietnam that the nutrition bar is a new sustainable line of FMCG products to be added to their portfolio.

Play became synonymous with **HIGH-ENERGY, HEALTHY** products, representing the lifestyle: “**EAT CLEAN, LIVE WELL**”

Sponsoring marathons: VNexpress Marathon 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023 in Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Quy Nhon, Hue, Ha Long; Long Bien Marathon 2020, 2021; Hanoi Heritage Marathon 2020; Techcombank HCM Marathon 2020; HCMC Run 2020; Ecopark Marathon 2021, 2023; Cuc Phuong Marathon 2023.

Sponsoring Vietnam Basketball Association (VBA) events: VBA 3x3 2022; VBA 5x5 2022; VBA 3x3 2023; VBA 5x5 2023.

3.2. Play Nutrition's products.

3.2.1. Categorizing Play Nutrition bars

According to Play Nutrition (2022), the current products of the company available on the market include the following product lines:

Natural and Healthy nut bars

Blueberry Cashew Flavor: cashews, blueberries, brown rice, oats, pumpkin seeds, pumpkin seeds, maltose syrup, fibre gum B, salt. Natural & Healthy nut bars.

Seaweed Cashew Flavor: cashews, seaweed, brown rice, oats, pumpkin seeds, pumpkin seeds, roasted soybeans, black sesame, maltose syrup, fibre gum B, salt.

Mushroom Flavor: cashews, shiitake mushrooms, brown rice, oats, roasted soybeans, pumpkin seeds, white sesame, malt extract, soluble fiber, tapioca starch, salt, brown rice oil, soy lecithin, chili powder, pepper powder, garlic powder, soy sauce extract.

Protein bar

Peanut Butter Flavor: protein milk mixture (calcium caseinate, concentrated whey, hydrolyzed whey protein), peanut butter (peanuts), soluble fiber (from corn and cane), red pumpkin seed powder, vegetable glycerin, sweeteners (stevia, erythritol), flavor (peanuts), citric acid, antioxidants (rosemary extract).

Cocoa Flavor: protein milk mixture (calcium caseinate, concentrated whey, soy protein isolate), soluble fiber (from corn fiber and cane fiber), cocoa mass (non-hydrogenated palm kernel oil, erythritol, cocoa powder), peanuts, sunflower butter, raisins, pure cocoa powder, cocoa butter, vegetable glycerin, fat-free red pumpkin seed powder, sweeteners (stevia, erythritol), flavors (chocolate, orange oil), sunflower lecithin, antioxidants (rosemary extract).

Apple Cinnamon Flavor: protein milk mixture (calcium caseinate, concentrated whey, hydrolyzed whey protein), fiber (from soluble corn fiber and cane fiber), almond butter, dried apples, fat-free red pumpkin seed powder, vegetable glycerin, cinnamon, sweeteners (stevia, erythritol), natural flavors (apple), citric acid, antioxidants (rosemary extract).

Energy bar

PLAY Energy Bar Macca & Peanut Butter Flavor: Peanut butter (21.4%), malt extract, corn starch, macadamia nuts (10%), oats, peanuts, cane syrup, soy protein powder, peanut powder, cacao nibs, puffed rice, digestive fiber, vegetable oil, vegetable glycerol, soy-based emulsifier, acid regulator, salt, rosemary extract.

PLAY Energy Bar Orange Cocoa Flavor: Cashews (21.5%), orange peel (10%), mango, dried grapes, peanut butter, cocoa powder, corn starch, soy protein powder, cane syrup, malt extract, puffed rice, cocoa butter, digestive fiber, vegetable oil, vegetable glycerol, soy-based emulsifier, acid regulator, salt, orange peel oil, rosemary extract.

PLAY Energy Bar Fruits & Oats Flavor: Cashews (23%), blueberries (15%), apricots (11.5%), dried grapes (11.5%), oats, corn starch, soy protein powder, malt extract, cane syrup, peanut butter, puffed rice, digestive fiber, vegetable oil, vegetable glycerol, soy-based emulsifier, acid regulator, salt, rosemary extract.

3.2.2. Strengths of Play Nutrition bars

The Play nutrition bar is a combination of various seeds and some grains. The absorption time is around 20 minutes. The bar contains high amounts of fiber (from the seeds) which provides a lasting feeling of fullness without feeling bloated. The energy provided is steady and lasts for about 3 hours, supporting effective mental and physical training and activities (Playnutrition, 2023a).

The nutrition components of the Play Nutrition energy bar mainly come from various seeds & malt, so the blood glycemic index (GI) is ensured to be higher than the GI of whole seeds and lower than the GI of processed foods (Playnutrition, 2023a).

Advantages of Play Nutrition energy bar

Helps provide energy for athletes and those with a high workload. The product contains nutrients from fruits and various seeds, offering balanced nutrition for the body.

It is completely vegan, contains good fats, and does not contain preservatives or refined sugar. It has salt which helps prevent cramps due to the loss of minerals while sweating during physical activity. The product is suitable for pregnant women and children. It is not suitable for people with diabetes (Play Nutrition, 2022a).

When running long distances, the fiber in these bars helps the body release energy slowly and makes you feel fuller for a longer period (Play Nutrition, 2022a).

Marathon runners are often susceptible to colds due to the extended duration and distances they run. Antioxidants and nutrients like selenium, vitamin E, zinc, etc. in the Energy Bars can help you recover and boost your immune system, especially the bars containing ingredients from dried fruits, cherries, and various seeds (Play Nutrition, 2022a)

After running for an extended period, you need nutrients such as carbohydrates, protein, and fiber. These nutrients help the body recover and curb hunger. Notably, these macronutrients can only be obtained through diet, as the body cannot produce them on its own. Therefore, a Protein Bar containing some fats, carbohydrates, and high protein content is excellent for physical recovery after a marathon. (Play Nutrition, 2022a)

Advantages of Play Nutrition protein bar

Helps supplement pure protein after gym workouts and bodybuilding. This product serves as a meal replacement before and after exercise due to its high protein content and quality carbs to replenish energy (Play Nutrition, 2022b).

Protein from 5 sources: Whey Protein Concentrate, Whey Protein Isolate, Whey Protein Hydrolyzed, Casein Protein, and Soy Isolate (Play Nutrition, 2022b).

The sweet flavor of the PLAY Protein Bar comes from the Stevia sweet herb – 100% natural, calorie-free, and especially safe for health. The special preparation formula, compared to ingredients from natural seeds and fruits, is rich in nutrients beneficial for health (Play Nutrition, 2022b).

Advantages of Play Nutrition Natural and Healthy nut bar

Suitable for a snack, breakfast, or a convenient lunch that's nutritious – Provides quick energy before and after exercising, sports, or work – The bars do not have added sugar, no flavorings – Made from 100% natural ingredients from nutrient-rich seeds – Very high in natural fiber which is good for digestion and the body's activity

– Rich in Omega 3,6,9 and some essential minerals like Calcium, Iron, Magnesium – Moderately salty taste, rich and delicious without causing satiety, enticing to the last bite! – Vegan bars suitable for vegetarians. – Suitable for those on a diet, losing weight, and taking care of their physique (Play Nutrition, 2022c).

The PLAY Natural & Healthy nutrition bar is a favorite snack for many people on a diet. The bar is made from various seeds that contain beneficial nutrients, providing a positive energy source for the body (Play Nutrition, 2022c).

4. Consumer Reviews on Digital Marketing Activities for Play Nutrition Energy Bars

4.1. Description of the participants of the survey

Graph 1: Age of participants

Source: Survey results

Of the 415 survey participants: 26 people are under 18 years old (6.3%), 28 people are between 18 and under 22 years old (6.7%), 108 people are between 22 and under 32 years old (26%), 176 people are between 32 and under 42 years old (42.4%), 73 people are between 42 and 52 years old (17.6%), and 4 people are over 52 years old (1%). Out of the 415 survey participants, 265 are male (63.9%), and 145 are female (35.9%). Regarding their living areas, 277 participants live in urban areas (66.7%) and 138 live in rural areas (33.3%)."

Graph 2: Survey participants' income

Source: Survey results

Regarding the income of the survey participants, the majority have an income ranging from 10 to 20 million VND (52%). The next group earns below 10 million VND (30%), and the remaining participants have an income above 20 million VND (18%).

4.2. Survey on accessibility and customers' evaluation of Play Nutrition energy bars

Graph 3: Percentage of survey participants who are aware of Play Nutrition bars.

Source: Survey results

With the convenience sampling method and the "snowball" method (a method where the next participant is found based on suggestions or referrals from a just-surveyed participant), out of 415 survey participants, 267 people had never heard of Play Nutrition products (64%). Only 148 people (36%) know of Play Nutrition's energy bars.

With 64% of surveyed individuals unaware of Play Nutrition products, it's clear that Play Nutrition's market coverage is limited, and its exposure is weak. This is understandable as the product was introduced to the market in 2015, starting with the distribution of SSP energy bars imported from the UK for 65,000 VND/bar (available at various golf courses nationwide). In 2016, they began contract manufacturing Protein Bars from Bulgaria priced at 45,000 VND/bar (covering Play Protein Bar in over 200 gyms nationwide). It wasn't until 2019 that they produced their first Play Energy Bar, priced at 25,000 VND/bar. By 2022, they launched the Natural & Healthy product for the mass market at 15,000 VND/bar (distributed through MT channels: Vinmart, Win+, Big C, CircleK, Family Mart, etc.). In 2023, there are plans to introduce strategic products and expand distribution on the GT channel. (Play Nutrition, 2023)

Of those who had never heard of the nutrition bars (267 people), 218 expressed interests in learning more about them. Among these 218 individuals, when asked about which Play Nutrition product lines, they wanted to learn more about, the results are shown in Graph 4.

Graph 4: Decisions when using Play Nutrition bars

Source: Survey results

Thus, the survey results indicate that the most interest is in the Natural and Healthy nut bar, with 163 out of 218 selections. Next is the energy bar with 133 out of 218 selections, and lastly, the protein bar with 118 out of 218 selections.

Graph 5: Approaching Digital Marketing Tools

Source: Survey results

Regarding the sources of Digital Marketing tools that customers want to use to learn about Play Nutrition energy bars: “Social Media Marketing” had the highest number of selections at 101; In second place was “Multimedia Marketing” with 53 selections; “Video Marketing” had 25 selections; “Influencer/Affiliate Marketing” had 23 selections; “Content Marketing” had 7 selections; “Blog Marketing” had 5 selections; “Search Engine Optimization (SEO)” had 4 selections.

For the 148 individuals who have used Play Nutrition energy bars, the sources from which they learned about the product are shown in Graph 6.

Graph 6: Sources of information about the nutrition bars

Source: Survey results

For those who are already aware of and have used the product, the most accessed sources of information about the nutrition bars are from “Friends/relatives/people around” with 84 selections, followed by “Social media pages” with 60 selections; “Websites, blogs” with 32 selections; “Search engines” with 20 selections; “Press/Media” with 24 selections; “Social media influencers” with 15 selections; “Advertisements integrated on social media pages” with 13 selections; and other channels labeled as “Other” with 4 selections.

Graph 7: Level of usage for the nutrition bars

Source: Survey results

Regarding the usage level of Play Nutrition bars, the survey results show that the number of users who use it “Occasionally” is 75 (51%), those who use it “Regularly” is 50 (34%); only 6 people use it “Very Frequently” (4%); and there are 17 people (11%) who “Know about the energy bar but have never used it”.

Graph 8: Usage rate of Play Nutrition bars

Source: Survey results

Among those who are aware of/have used Play Nutrition bars, the number of people who have consumed the “Energy Bar” is 64; the “Protein Bar” is 43; and the “Natural and Healthy Nut Bar” is 90.

Graph 9: Pros of Play Nutrition bars

Source: Survey results

Based on the survey results, the biggest advantage of the Play Nutrition energy bar is “Energy Boost for Athletes and High-Intensity Workers”, chosen by 90 respondents; next is “Provides Balanced Nutrition & Weight Control” by 59 respondents. “Natural, Vegan, Nutrient-Rich from Fruits and Seeds” Another 59. Finally, “Quick & Long-Lasting Energy, Improved Concentration, and Convenience” with 33 respondents

4.3. Evaluating the implementation of Digital Marketing tools for Play Nutrition energy bars.

The study surveyed the frequency of appearance, attractiveness, and influence of the Digital Marketing tools for the Play Nutrition energy bar product. The results are as follows:

Table 1: Frequency of appearance of Digital Marketing tools for the Play Nutrition bar

	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Evaluation of frequency	Order of frequency of appearance
Social Media Marketing	26	28	52	33	9	2.80	Normal	4
Influencer/Affiliate	25	40	43	29	11	2.74	Normal	5
Multimedia Marketing	25	33	42	40	8	2.82	Normal	3
Search Engine Optimization	23	35	44	33	13	2.85	Normal	2
Video Marketing	24	36	43	33	12	2.82	Normal	3
Content marketing	20	34	46	35	13	2.91	Normal	1
Blog marketing	27	38	41	31	11	2.74	Normal	5

Convention: 1. Never; 2. Rarely; 3. Sometimes; 4. Often; 5. Very often.

Source: Survey results

The survey results show that among Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools, the average frequency score ranges from 2.74 to 2.91, indicating that these tools appear "Sometimes". Amongst them, **“Content marketing” has the highest score (2.91 points)**, and **“SEO – Search Engine Optimization”** ranks second (2.85 points). The lowest scores are for **“Blog marketing”** and **“Influencer/Affiliate”** tools, both with a score of 2.74.

Graph 10: The frequency of appearance of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools
Source: Survey results

Table 2: The level of attractiveness of the digital marketing tools for the digital marketing product

	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Evaluation of frequency	Order of frequency of appearance
Social Media Marketing	23	20	52	39	14	3.01	Normal	6
Influencer/Affiliate	20	27	55	30	16	2.97	Normal	7
Multimedia Marketing	18	21	60	35	14	3.04	Normal	5
Search Engine Optimization	17	24	54	39	14	3.06	Normal	3
Video Marketing	18	25	49	37	19	3.09	Normal	2
Content marketing	19	23	47	42	17	3.10	Normal	1
Blog marketing	16	27	54	36	15	3.05	Normal	4

Convention: 1. Very Unappealing; 2. Unappealing; 3. Normal; 4. Appealing; 5. Very Appealing
Source: Survey results

According to the survey results, regarding the attractiveness level of Play Nutrition's digital marketing tools, the average converted scores fluctuate between 2.97 and 3.1, which falls into the “Moderate” attractiveness category. Among these tools, **“Content marketing” has the highest score (3.1 points)**, followed by **“Video Marketing”** in second place (3.09 points), and the lowest score is for the **“Influencer/Affiliate”** tool at 2.97 points.

Graph 11: The attractiveness level of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools
Source: Survey results

Table 3: The attractiveness level of Play Nutrition's digital marketing tools

	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Evaluation of frequency	Order of frequency of appearance
Social Media Marketing	23	22	53	38	12	2.96	Normal	4
Influencer/Affiliate	12	34	53	39	10	3.01	Normal	3
Multimedia Marketing	16	24	61	30	17	3.05	Normal	2
Search Engine Optimization	15	29	54	40	10	3.01	Normal	3
Video Marketing	16	28	49	40	15	3.07	Normal	1
Content marketing	15	27	53	39	14	3.07	Normal	1
Blog marketing	14	32	54	34	14	3.01	Normal	3

Convention: 1. Very Uninfluential; 2. Not Influential; 3. Moderate; 4. Influential; 5. Very Influential

Source: Survey results

According to the survey results, for the influence level of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools, the average scores converted into a range from 2.96 to 3.07. This indicates that the tools have a "Moderate" level of influence. Amongst them, **"Content marketing" has the highest score (3.07 points), with "Video Marketing" (3.07 points),** and the lowest score is for the "Social Media Marketing" tool with a score of 2.96.

Graph 12: The influence level of Play Nutrition's Digital Marketing tools

Source: Survey results

5. Completing Digital Marketing Tools for Play Nutrition Bars

5.1. Orientation for improving the Digital Marketing tools of Play Nutrition

- **For the niche market.** The company focuses on specific target customers for Play's unique products. Concentrating on consumers who are athletes, or those who require high levels of concentration, and intellectual labor... these are potential customers because their demand for energy supplements is higher than the average consumer due to the nature of their work. Additionally, there's an emphasis on brand-building, improving packaging, and design to attract these customers, especially for the **Protein bar** and **Energy bar** product lines.

- **For the mass market.** This market targets all customer groups, from young to old, prioritizing those with specific dietary needs, such as people with obesity, and type 1 diabetes... who need to control their calorie intake. Additionally, other potential consumers include pregnant women... who require a complete nutrient intake. For the mass market, the company promotes the 'Natural and Healthy' bars, which can meet the needs of the above-mentioned customer segments.

5.2. Some recommendations to improve the Digital Marketing tool for Play Nutrition bars

From the survey results of the research group, Play Nutrition's "Content Marketing" tool leads in terms of frequency, attractiveness, and influence on the surveyed subjects. Therefore, businesses need to continue to promote brand content, and the benefits of Play Nutrition bars, ensuring appropriate, quality content. To optimize this digital marketing tool, businesses need to:

- *Plan to build content to promote the brand and the function of nutrition bars for consumers in detail.*
- *Once there are articles about the product, posting frequency plays an important role in assessing the effectiveness of this digital marketing tool. Businesses need to allocate a reasonable posting time, with at least 2-3 posts per week on websites or social media pages to expand the reach of the content for the target customers.*
- *Provide accurate, trustworthy information. In addition to brand-promoting content, and introducing the product's functionality, businesses can integrate some content, and useful information about nutrition, and healthy eating habits... to score points with potential customers.*

Play Nutrition's "**Video Marketing**" tool, also leads in terms of influence on customers using Play Nutrition bars. It can be assessed that this is a promising digital marketing tool currently and in the future for the company's product lines. To optimize this digital marketing tool, businesses should combine it with the "Content Marketing" tool, creating product introductions and promotional videos. Promotional videos need to focus on sound quality and sharp images, attracting all customer segments. In addition, the video needs meticulous preparation, not too long but still ensures the content to be conveyed, as too long will be boring and not focused on a specific aspect, while too short will not fully convey the content to the target customers.

Although the "**Influencer/Affiliate Marketing**" tool does not have the same influence and appeal to survey participants as other tools, it is considered a strength of the company. The company needs to promote and develop this digital marketing tool. To maximize the efficiency of the "**Influencer/Affiliate**" tool, businesses need to:

- *Continue using Influencers to build market trust. The company's potential is having a brand ambassador who is a SEA Games athlete and Ironman for the triathlon (running, cycling, swimming) – the company needs sponsorship activities to continue using his image. Moreover, the company should continue to approach other KOLs like basketball and street soccer KOLs - each sport will have a representative for Play, combining to build both their brand and Play's brand.*
- *For affiliate marketing, businesses need to go through influencers. This is a promising tool to target the mass market, with two main directions: one is brand building, and the second is promoting sales, creating a shared network to build personal brands, and promoting product lines to all Play's target customers.*

The "**Media Marketing**" tool is the tool that survey participants most want to access when wanting to learn about Play Nutrition bars. Therefore, businesses need to continue to develop social media platforms and maximize media channels. Especially targeting platforms with a trading floor like TikTok to promote the brand, apply voucher systems, and exclusive promotions of the e-commerce platform. Given the current trend, the target customers will mainly be the younger generation, so TikTok is a potential channel, both easily accessible to target customers and solving the problem of both building the brand and pushing sales, as TikTok has platforms like TikTok shop, TikTok business account.

Businesses also need to exploit available resources. Promote website development, run ads, and promote product brands on strong platforms like Google, as Google has separate segments like the Google Network, Google Display Network, and keyword optimization (SEO) linked to the website. Make the most of available resources, namely the Play Nutrition website, which integrates e-commerce websites for ordering, both building the brand and boosting sales.

6. Conclusion

In today's rapidly evolving era, Digital Marketing channels are gradually replacing and equating with traditional marketing channels. While traditional marketing solely focuses on "making an impression", Digital Marketing

shifts to a new perspective, allowing users to experience products and services, especially in the age of the Internet explosion. Along with the introduction of health-beneficial products, Play Nutrition also targets a vibrant, modern lifestyle, always full of energy to conquer challenges and focuses on the niche market as well as gradually conquering the mass market in the future. The continued refinement of Digital Marketing tools for Play Nutrition bars is essential for the brand to be increasingly affirmed and developed. Play is not just a brand but a lifestyle.

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References

- Adsmo (2022). *What is Digital Marketing - Comprehensive competition for businesses in the 4.0 era*. <https://adsmo.vn/digital-marketing-la-gi/> (Accessed 20/7/2023)
- banhmgachdo.com (2023). *What are energy bars and the benefits of energy bars?* <https://banhmgachdo.com/thanh-nang-luong-la-gi-va-loi-ich-cua-thanh-nang-luong>, Accessed 24/06/2023)
- bazanland.com (2021). *5 Benefits of Energy Bars for Sports Practitioners*. <https://bazanland.com/granola/loi-ich-cua-thanh-nang-luong/>
- Chaffey, D., Ellis-Chadwick, F., Mayer, R., Johnston, K. (2009). *Internet Marketing: Strategy, Implementation and Practice*. 4th Edition. Prentice Hall.
- Hoai Phuong (2023). *Benefits of energy bars in running*. <https://vnexpress.net/loi-ich-cua-thanh-nang-luong-trong-chay-bo-4575345>
- Le Si Tri (2018). *Online Marketing - New solution for tourism promotion*. <http://thuvienso.bvu.edu.vn/handle/TVDHBRVT/19051>
- Lan Anh (2023). *Play Nutrition accompanies the Vietnam professional basketball tournament VBA* <https://vnexpress.net/play-nutrition-dong-hanh-voi-giai-bong-ro-chuyen-nghiep-viet-nam-vba-4617860.html>
- Nguyen Thi Thu Thuy (2008). *Marketing via the Internet and practical application in Vietnam*. Master thesis. Foreign Trade University. ocd. vn (2023). *What is digital marketing? The role of digital marketing in the digital age*. <https://ocd.vn/digital-marketing-la-gi-vai-tro-cua-digital-marketing-trong-thoi-dai-so/> (Accessed 12/7/2023)
- ooc.vn (2022). *The impact of Digital Marketing on businesses*. https://ooc.vn/anh-huong-cua-digital-marketing-doi-voi-doanh-nghiep/#Canh_tranh (Accessed 20/7/2023)
- Pham Thanh Cong (2020). *Discussion on electronic marketing applications in retail in Vietnam (2020)*. <https://tapchicongthuong.vn/bai-viet/luan-ban-ve-ung-dung-marketing-dien-tu-trong-ban-le-o-viet-nam-74314.htm>, accessed 26/6/2023.
- Philip Kotler (2007). *Basic marketing*. Social Labor Publishing House Philip Kotler & Armstrong (2007). *Marketing – An Introduction*. Prentice Hall Publishing House
- Play nutrition (2020). *4 Benefits of Energy Bars and Protein Bars for Long Distance Runners*. <https://playnutrition.vn/4-loi-ich-cua-thanh-nang-luong-va-thanh-protein-doi-voi-nguoi-chay-bo-duong-dai-2/>
- Playnutrition (2022a). *Play Nutrition energy bars*. <https://playnutrition.vn/san-pham/hop-12-thanh-nang-luong-play-phien-ban-2-0-vi-trai-cay-yen-mach/>. Accessed 7/08/2023.
- Playnutrition (2022b). *Play Nutrition protein bars*. <https://playnutrition.vn/thanh-protein/>. Accessed 24/7/2023.
- Playnutrition (2022c). *Play Nutrition Nut Bars*. <https://playnutrition.vn/san-pham/combo-thanh-hat-dinh-duong-natural-healthy/>. Accessed 8/8/2023.

Play Nutrition (2023). *About Play*. Playbook

Playnutrition (2023a). *Why does eating play cake bars keep you full for a long time and maintain your endurance?*

<https://www.facebook.com/playnutrition.vn/posts/pfbid023rdLZHNyoMciFJEAs8YqpZc9fRdUTUTyQsn2XKt8JLjrGCeNFVojJy74ZDRFKQhsl>

Ružić, D. (2003). *E–marketing*. Osijek. Ekonomski fakultet Osijek.